

Effects of plasma treatment of digestates on pH, nitrification and nitrogen turnover during storage and after soil application

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ABSTRACT

Acidification through plasma treatment technology presents a potential solution to mitigate nitrogen losses throughout the manure management chain, offering a dual benefit of atmospheric nitrogen incorporation into manures while inducing acidification. This study evaluated the use and effectiveness of plasma treatment technology as a one-time acidification strategy for digested slurry during long-term storage, its effects on slurry nitrogen (N) availability and subsequent release in the soil. A digestate from a full-scale anaerobic digester was separated using a decanter centrifuge, and the resultant liquid fraction (LF) was plasma treated to achieve three different initial pH levels (4.27, 5.03 and 5.42). After that, a storage experiment was set up for 180 days to monitor the evolution in pH and changes in NH_4^+ , NO_3^- and NO_2^- . Concurrently, a soil incubation experiment was conducted to study the N turnover for 80 days after incorporating the organic materials (Liquid fraction, plasma-treated liquid fractions, digestate and raw slurry). Plasma treatment significantly increased total N and the proportion of inorganic N in the slurries by fixing atmospheric N as NO_3^- and NO_2^- and reduced the slurry pH depending on the treatment duration. After six months of storage, pH increased by 0.91 pH units in the plasma-treated liquid fraction with the highest initial pH (LFpH-5.42). Plasma treatment significantly increased net inorganic N release in soil by 5–14 % compared to a non-treated liquid fraction. Unexpected prolonged inhibition of NH_4^+ nitrification in soil for over 80 days after applying plasma-treated slurries was observed. In conclusion, plasma treatment emerges as a promising alternative to acid- and bio-acidification strategies, offering prolonged low slurry pH stabilisation, improved fertiliser value and delayed NH_4^+ -N nitrification in soil.

1. Introduction

Ammonia (NH_3) volatilisation from livestock production is a major source of atmospheric emissions and harmful micro-particles, and it is of concern as it happens throughout the management chain from manure handling in animal houses, storage and field applications (Kai et al., 2008). The emissions result in serious environmental issues associated with the deposition of NH_3 and ammonium (NH_4^+), such as eutrophication and air quality issues. Moreover, for farmers, NH_3 emissions reduce plant available NH_4^+ in manures, reducing their fertiliser value (Sørensen & Amato, 2002). The long-term storage of manure prior to its field application could result in significant emissions of NH_3 and greenhouse gases, i.e. methane (Petersen et al., 2012). In addition, the field application of manure

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poses a high risk of NH_3 emissions, which is exacerbated if a digestate with high pH and dry matter content is used (Pedersen et al., 2021). As a result, measures should be put in place to reduce NH_3 emissions in all steps of manure handling.

Slurry treatment via acidification with concentrated sulfuric acid (H_2SO_4) has been used to reduce NH_3 emissions during storage and field application (Fangueiro et al., 2015a; Kai et al., 2008; Sørensen & Eriksen, 2009). Slurry acidification reduces NH_3 emissions by modifying slurry characteristics and shifting the chemical equilibrium from volatile non-ionised NH_3 form towards non-volatile ionised NH_4^+ form (Fangueiro et al., 2015a; Pedersen & Nyord, 2023). Moreover, acidification influences the turnover of organic matter in manures during storage and hence its nitrogen (N) availability (Hjorth et al., 2015; Sørensen & Eriksen, 2009). Slurry acidification can be implemented in-house, at storage tanks or just before field application. Due to its high buffering capacity, the slurry pH may return to its initial pH for in-house and storage tank acidification, reducing its effectiveness (Husted et al., 2006).

The wide use of concentrated H_2SO_4 compared to other inorganic acids for slurry acidification is linked to its relatively low cost and efficiency in lowering slurry pH (Fangueiro et al., 2015a; Ma et al., 2022). However, acidification with H_2SO_4 is still at a cost, as around 5–7 kg of the acid per ton of slurry has to be used to lower the pH to 5.5, with even a larger acid dosage required to lower the pH of digestates due to their high buffering capacity. Furthermore, the technology is ineffective in the acidification of slurries and digestates in the field due to extensive foaming, increased risk of sulphur over-fertilisation, a limitation for use in certified organic production, and potential risks associated with the use of acids such as corrosiveness and development of volatile sulphur-containing compounds (Kai et al., 2008; Pedersen & Nyord, 2023).

Alternative strategies for sulphuric acid acidification, such as bio-acidification, have recently been explored (Prado et al., 2020; Regueiro et al., 2022). Bio-acidification could be achieved by adding easily degradable organic substrates/organic acids to the slurry, followed by their degradation in oxygen deficiency conditions by microorganisms present in the slurry as described by Regueiro et al. (2022). Similar to sulphuric acid-based acidification, this strategy faces numerous limitations. For instance, the organic acids utilised are often weak, requiring large quantities to attain a target pH; the acids degrade pretty fast, possibly increasing slurry pH to its initial pH within a short period during storage (Bittman et al., 2014). Moreover, bio-acidification may be limited by the availability of sufficient quantities of suitable, fermentable residues as substrates (Regueiro et al., 2022). For this reason, this study explores a new novel plasma treatment technique developed by a Norwegian Agritech company, N2 Applied (Asker, Norway), as an alternative to sulfuric acid-based acidification and bio-acidification. The technology aims to reduce NH_3 emissions during storage and field application of slurries, limits CH_4 emissions, and increases available inorganic N in slurries (N2-Applied, 2023).

The plasma treatment by the N2 Applied technology fixes reactive nitrogen from the atmosphere to the slurries in NO_3^- and NO_2^- forms (Graves et al., 2018; N2-Applied, 2023). The plasma ionizes air with a strong electric field, making nitrogen and oxygen to form reactive nitrogen gas. The reactive nitrogen gas is then absorbed into the liquid, enriching it with nitrogen. During plasma treatment, hydrogen peroxide (H_2O_2) and peroxyxynitrite (ONOO^-) are additionally formed in the solutions (Graves et al., 2019). The fixation of NO_3^- and NO_2^- forms nitric acid (HNO_3) and nitrous acid (HNO_2), lowering the slurry pH and thereby reducing the risk of NH_3 emissions.

Plasma treatment of slurry has shown a potential to replace more mineral fertiliser and increase yields compared to untreated slurry (Cottis et al., 2023; Mousavi et al., 2022), alongside reducing both CH_4 and NH_3 emissions during storage and field applications (Graves et al., 2018). However, its use and effectiveness as a one-time acidification strategy for slurries during long-term tank storage before field application are unknown. The potential of achieving and keeping a constant pH throughout the slurry storage period by one-time acidification can save resources and protect the environment (Overmeyer et al., 2021).

Plasma treatment to achieve different target pH could result in varying amounts of NO_3^- and NO_2^- fixed in the slurries. Despite NO_2^- being part of the biological nitrogen assimilation pathway, high NO_2^- levels in the soil, especially by slurry injection, may cause toxicity in the soil-plant system, especially to the roots at their earlier stages of development (Pedersen et al., 2020; Zsoldos et al., 1993). The fate of undesirable NO_2^- fixed and the effect of plasma treatment on nitrification after slurry soil incorporation is also not documented. Also, whether the beneficial gains of fixing NO_3^- and NO_2^- to the slurry are counterbalanced by other N losses during slurry storage and soil incorporation are unknown.

The objectives of this study were to a) evaluate the pH stability of the liquid fraction of a digestate during prolonged storage following plasma-assisted acidification, b) evaluate the effects of plasma-assisted acidification to different initial target pH during plasma treatment on N availability in soil, and c) investigate the dynamics of nitrogen forms (NH_4^+ , NO_3^- and NO_2^-) during 6-month storage and following soil incorporation. We hypothesized that i) the lower the pH of the plasma-treated liquid fraction of the digestate, the higher the content of NO_3^- -N and NO_2^- -N added, and subsequently, the higher the net inorganic N release following soil incorporation and ii) the lower the pH in plasma treated liquid fraction of the digestate, the more stable the pH is during storage.

2. Material and methods

2.1. Organic materials and solid-liquid separation

The digestate used for this experiment was sourced from a 3400 m³ full-scale secondary reactor with a hydraulic retention time (HRT) of 30 days after primary digestion in a 1200 m³ full-scale primary reactor with a HRT of 15 days. Both the primary and secondary biogas reactors were operated at thermophilic temperatures (52 °C). The inputs to the primary reactor included 75 % cattle slurry and 25 % solid biomass containing grass silage, grass, deep litter, meadow grass, straw, organic meadow grass and organic grass silage. The liquid fraction (LF) was collected from a storage tank after solid-liquid separation of the digestate from the secondary reactor using a decanter centrifuge (Model UCD 305–00–02, GEA Westfalia, Germany).

2.2. Plasma treatment of the liquid fraction of the digestate

The liquid fraction (LF) was plasma treated using the N2 Applied plasma unit, which works by fixing atmospheric nitrogen as nitrogen oxides (NO_x) using electricity. The gaseous NO_x react with the slurry to form nitric acid (HNO_3) and nitrous acid (HNO_2), which lowers the pH. The pH of the resultant plasma-treated slurry depends on the amount of nitrogen absorbed into the slurry, and energy consumption is increased proportionally to how much nitrogen is fixed. Increasing the treatment intensity increases the amount of atmospheric N fixed, increasing the slurry's acidity. Lower pH is achieved by applying more energy to increase the concentration of nitrogen and oxygen in the plasma to achieve high concentrations of reactive N. Once the desired pH set point is achieved, the slurry is exported from the N2 Applied unit.

The energy needed to achieve a set pH depends on the slurry's buffering capacity. A less buffered slurry (i.e. cattle slurry) will take less energy to treat than a highly buffered slurry (i.e. a biogas digestate). In this experiment, the power consumption was 60 kWh/kg NO_x -N fixed during plasma treatment. The digestate separation before plasma treatment is based on the current design of the N2-Applied unit, which can only handle small particles < 3 mm to avoid clogging. For this experiment, the pH of the plasma-treated slurries was pH 4.27 (LFpH-4.27), pH 5.03 (LFpH-5.03) and pH 5.42 (LFpH-5.42). The selection of pH \approx 5.5 was based on the current practice of slurry acidification in barns. In contrast, a selection of lower pH (4.27 and 5.03) was tested to investigate the effects of plasma treatment to a lower pH on N availability and pH stability during storage. The plasma treatments were made on different days, which entailed adjusting operating parameters. It is noteworthy that no foaming was observed during plasma treatment.

2.3. Storage experiment setup

The storage experiment consisted of six treatments in triplicate of raw slurry, digestate, a liquid fraction (LF) and the three plasma-treated liquid fractions (LFpH-4.27, LFpH-5.03 and LFpH-5.42). Around 12 kg of the organic materials were transferred into 15 kg plastic buckets (height = 0.30 m, diameter = 0.28 m) after homogenization in 100 L holding containers using a laboratory scale electric-powered stirrer for two minutes and stored for 180 days at 10 °C to adequately assess pH development and changes in nitrogen forms, depicting mean annual temperatures in Denmark. The treatments were covered with lids pierced with a hole in the centre (0.5 cm diameter) to allow for air exchange without evaporation losses. A portion of the organic materials (5 kg of each treatment) used for the storage experiment were stored at -18 °C prior to their use in the soil incubation experiments. At days 0, 30, 60, 90, 120, 150 and 180, subsamples (100 mL) were collected from each container after moderate stirring (using an electric-powered stirrer at low speed) for analysis of pH, NH_4^+ -N, NO_3^- -N, and NO_2^- -N. Total N, total C, dry matter content and volatile solids were also analysed on samples taken on days 0 and 180.

2.4. Soil incubation study

The soil utilised for this study was collected from Aarhus University experimental farm, Foulumgaard (56°30' N, 09°35' E), at Research Centre Foulum from the top 0–20 cm plough layer in March 2022. The soil is a loamy sand with a pH (1:2.5 H_2O) of 6.18 and contains 83 g clay kg^{-1} , 284 g silt kg^{-1} , 610 g sand kg^{-1} , 31 g organic matter kg^{-1} , 15.6 g total carbon kg^{-1} and 1.3 g total N kg^{-1} . The soil was air-dried for a week and then sieved through a < 2 mm sieve to remove stones and larger plant residues. The soil was then homogenized, moistened and pre-incubated at 10°C until the start of the experiment.

The incubation experiments entailed weighing 50 g of soil, based on dry matter weight, into a 250 mL polyethylene bottle, then adding organic materials at a 200 mg N kg^{-1} soil rate. This was followed by adding another 50 g equivalent of dry soil to cover the organic materials. A control treatment with non-amended soil was included.

Water was added to each polyethylene bottle to achieve a moisture level equivalent to 55% of the water holding capacity (WHC), optimal for microbial activity and just low enough to limit denitrification. The bottles were covered with hole-pierced parafilm to prevent high water loss through evaporation while ensuring aeration throughout the incubation period. Each of the eight treatments was replicated 21 times to allow three replicates to be destructively sampled for analysis on days 0, 3, 7, 14, 28, 50 and 80, giving a total of 168 samples.

Incubation occurred at 10 °C in a dark room, simulating average soil temperatures in spring under field conditions in Denmark. Soil moisture content was monitored weekly and adjusted based on the initial weights to maintain a constant WHC. On each sampling day, the soil was removed from the polyethylene containers and homogenized in trays, and portions of 25 g were extracted with 100 mL of 1 M KCl by mechanical shaking for a half-hour (end-over-end) for inorganic N (NO_3^- -N, NO_2^- -N and exchangeable NH_4^+ -N) analysis. Soil pH (in soil extracts) and soil moisture content were measured on each destructive sampling day. Extracts were frozen at -18 °C until analyses.

2.5. Analytical methods

The Total Kjeldahl nitrogen (TKN) in the organic materials was analysed according to APHA (2005) by the Kjeldahl digestion method (Kjeltec™ 8400, Foss Analytical CO. LTD, Hillerød, Denmark). NH_4^+ -N and total oxidised nitrogen (TON), comprising of NO_3^- -N and NO_2^- -N in the organic materials and soil extracts, were analysed by Auto Analyzer AA500 flow colourimetry (Seal Analytical GmbH, Norderstedt, Germany) after 1 M KCl extraction as per Sommer et al. (1992). The NO_2^- -N content was determined colourimetrically using a Thermo Spectronic Helios UV-Visible spectrophotometer (Artisan Technology Group®, Champaign, Illinois, USA) according to the procedure described by Keeney and Nelson (1983). The total N in the organic materials was calculated as the

summation of the TKN + TON (NO₃-N + NO₂-N), with Nitrate-N being determined as the difference between TON and NO₂-N.

Dry matter, volatile solids and ash contents in substrates and digestates were analysed according to the standard methods (APHA, 2005). The dry matter content of the soil and organic materials was determined by drying the samples to a constant weight at 105 °C for 24 hours. Volatile solids were determined by loss on ignition at 550 °C for 6 hours. Volatile fatty acids were analysed using 7890 A gas chromatography with a flame ionization detector (Agilent Technologies Inc., California, USA). Total carbon content was analysed using the Dumas combustion method with a vario MAX cube elemental analyser (Elementar Analysensysteme GmbH, Langenselbold, Germany). The soil pH was measured in water extract (1:2.5 w/w) with a PHM220 pH meter (Meterlab® Radiometer, Copenhagen, Denmark).

2.6. Calculations and statistical analysis

The net inorganic N release in the soil (% of N applied) from the organic materials was calculated as the difference between the total inorganic N (TIN) in the amended soils with organic materials and control soils without any amendment divided by total applied N (TN) as per Eq. 1.

$$\text{Net inorganic N release (\% of N input)} = \frac{TIN_{\text{Treatment}} - TIN_{\text{control}}}{TN_{\text{Applied}}} \times 100 \% \quad (1)$$

It was assumed that nitrous oxide and denitrification losses of N from the soils were either negligible or similar from all the treatments after the incorporation of materials. Similarly, clay fixation of ammonium-N was assumed to be negligible. The recovered NH₄⁺ (% of applied NH₄⁺) at each extraction day was calculated for each of the treatments using Eq. 2, where NH₄⁺-N_{trt} and NH₄⁺-N_{control} are the concentrations of the NH₄⁺-N (mg NH₄⁺-N kg⁻¹) in the treatment and control, respectively, at any given time after the incorporation of the organic materials.

$$\text{Recovered NH}_4^+ \text{ (\% of applied NH}_4^+) = \frac{NH_4^+ - N_{(trt)} - NH_4^+ - N_{(control)}}{\text{Applied NH}_4^+ - N} \times 100 \% \quad (2)$$

Nitrification rates (mg N kg⁻¹ day⁻¹) after organic material incorporation were calculated as per Eq. 3, where TON_(time-y) and TON_(time-x) represent a change of TON (NO₃-N + NO₂-N) at a time (days) interval divided by the number of days taken for the change to occur.

$$\text{Nitrification rate (mg N kg}^{-1}\text{ day}^{-1}) = \frac{TON_{(time-y)} - TON_{(time-x)}}{(y - x) \text{ days}} \quad (3)$$

Net inorganic N mineralisation after 80 days of incubation was calculated as the difference in the net inorganic N release (NiN-release) at day 80 and net inorganic N release at day 0 divided by applied organic N as shown in Eq. 4;

$$\text{N mineralisation (\%)} = \frac{NiN_{\text{release}_{\text{day80}}} - NiN_{\text{release}_{\text{day0}}}}{\text{applied organic N}} \times 100 \% \quad (4)$$

All statistical analyses were done using R statistical software version 4.0.3 (R Core Team, 2020). The effect of plasma-assisted acidification of the organic materials on the net inorganic N release in the soil after incorporation, soil pH, recovered NH₄⁺ (% of applied NH₄⁺), and nitrification rates (mg N kg⁻¹ day⁻¹) were determined using one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA). When the treatment effect was significant, the treatments' differences were tested using the post hoc Tukey's Honestly Significant Difference (HSD) statistical test using *emmeans* R-package. Shapiro-Wilk tests, quantile-quantile plots and visual examination of the residuals against the fitted values were performed to confirm normality and homoscedasticity assumptions in all dependent variables. In cases where data deviated from the normal distribution, it was log-transformed. A significance level of p ≤ 0.05 was used for all statistical

Table 1

Main characteristics of raw slurry, digestate, the liquid fraction of separated digestates (LF) and plasma-treated liquid fractions at different initial target pH used for storage and soil incubation. Values represent means and standard deviations in brackets (n=3).

Material	Units	Raw slurry	Digestate	LF	LFpH-4.27	LFpH-5.03	LFpH-5.42)
Dry matter	%	4.44 ± 0.05	6.21 ± 0.12	3.00 ± 0.03	3.81 ± 0.11	3.56 ± 0.08	3.66 ± 0.02
Volatile solids	% of FM	3.48 ± 0.03	4.80 ± 0.10	2.00 ± 0.03	2.89 ± 0.10	2.69 ± 0.03	2.68 ± 0.03
Ash content	% of FM	0.96 ± 0.03	1.41 ± 0.02	1.00 ± 0.00	0.92 ± 0.02	0.89 ± 0.05	0.98 ± 0.01
pH	-	7.05 ± 0.05	7.86 ± 0.02	7.99 ± 0.01	4.27 ± 0.01	5.03 ± 0.06	5.42 ± 0.01
Total N	g kg ⁻¹ FM	2.44 ± 0.16	3.28 ± 0.14	2.94 ± 0.01	5.15 ± 0.21	4.56 ± 0.09	4.91 ± 0.04
NH ₄ ⁺ -N	g kg ⁻¹ FM	1.23 ± 0.02	1.77 ± 0.02	1.73 ± 0.02	1.40 ± 0.01	1.11 ± 0.01	1.25 ± 0.01
NO ₃ -N	g kg ⁻¹ FM	bdl	bdl	bdl	2.37 ± 0.04	1.87 ± 0.00	1.06 ± 0.10
NO ₂ -N	g kg ⁻¹ FM	bdl	bdl	bdl	0.19 ± 0.01	0.26 ± 0.00	1.10 ± 0.09
Total carbon	g kg ⁻¹ FM	18.0 ± 0.54	20.3 ± 0.83	12.2 ± 0.16	11.3 ± 1.73	14.6 ± 0.26	15.2 ± 0.88
Total VFA	g kg ⁻¹ FM	3.28 ± 0.02	0.13 ± 0.02	0.85 ± 0.00	1.22 ± 0.03	0.69 ± 0.02	0.82 ± 0.01
NH ₄ ⁺ + TON	% of TN	50.6	54	59.1	77.1	71.1	69.4
C/N	ratio	7.4	6.2	4.1	2.1	3.2	3.1

FM= fresh matter, VFA = volatile fatty acid, TON = total oxidised nitrogen (NO₃-N + NO₂-N), Total N= Total Kjeldahl N+ TON, bdl=below detection limits.

tests.

3. Results

3.1. Effects of plasma treatment on organic materials characteristics

The physico-chemical characteristics of the organic materials are summarised in Table 1. The dry matter content (DM) ranged from 3.0 % to 6.2 %. The digestate separation reduced the DM concentration in liquid fraction (LF) by 52 % compared to the unseparated digestate. The plasma-treated samples (LFpH-4.27, LFpH-5.03 and LFpH-5.42) had significantly higher DM content relative to the untreated LF. The pH of the organic materials ranged from pH 4.27 to pH 7.99. The different pH levels in plasma-treated materials (LFpH-4.27, LFpH-5.03 and LFpH-5.42) were achieved by varying the treatment intensities, which dissolved varying amounts of NO_x-rich acidic gas (Table 1).

The raw slurry, digestate and LF did not have NO₃-N and NO₂-N content, while plasma-treated samples had variable amounts of NO₃-N and NO₂-N. At low pH, NO₃-N was significantly higher, whereas NO₂-N was higher at a higher treatment pH of 5.42 (LFpH-5.42). The fixation of NO₃-N and NO₂-N to the treated samples significantly increased the total N by 1.62–2.21 g kg⁻¹ compared to the untreated LF. Furthermore, the treatment increased the proportion of inorganic N (NO₃-N + NO₂-N + NH₄⁺-N) as a % of total N by 10–18 % units, with the raw slurry and digestate having the lowest proportion at 51 and 54%, respectively (Table 1).

The raw slurry and the digestate had the highest proportion of total C content and C/N ratio compared to the LF and plasma-treated liquid fractions of the digestate. Before storage, the total volatile fatty acids (VFA) concentrations were highest in the raw slurry and lowest in the digestate. The plasma-treated slurries had a lower concentration of NH₄⁺-N by 0.33–0.63 g kg⁻¹ relative to the untreated LF (Table 1).

3.2. Effects of plasma treatment on the evolution of pH and digestate properties during storage

In the first 30 days of storage, there was an increase in the pH, with the highest increase occurring in LF and LFpH-5.42 treatments by 0.11 and 0.28 pH units, respectively. On the contrary, during the same period, pH decreased in the digestate, where pH decreased by 0.25 pH units after 60 days of storage (Fig. 1). After 90 days, pH gradually increased in all the organic materials, but not significantly. However, the increase in the digestate after day 60 did not exceed the initial digestate pH. During this period, the highest change in pH occurred in this order: LFpH-5.42 > LF > LFpH-5.03 = Raw slurry > LFpH-4.27. After day 90, the pH remained constant with minimal changes until the last day of storage except for LFpH-5.03 and LFpH-5.42, which had a sharp and significant increase

Fig. 1. : Evolution in NH₄⁺-N, NO₂⁻-N, NO₃⁻-N and pH in raw slurry, digestate, the liquid fraction of separated digestates (LF) and plasma-treated liquid fractions at different initial target pH (pH 4.27, pH 5.03 and pH 5.42) during storage for 180 days at 10 °C. Error bars represent standard deviation (n = 3). The letters indicate significant differences (p < 0.05) in the concentrations of NO₂⁻-N and NO₃⁻-N in the plasma-treated samples at each sampling interval of 30 days.

Table 2

Changes (Δ) in dry matter, total C, total N, NH_4^+ -N, NO_3^- -N, NO_2^- -N and proportion of inorganic N (NH_4^+ + NO_2^- + NO_3^-) to total N after 180 days of storage of different organic manure types at 10 °C for 180 days (6 months).

Material	Dry matter %			Total C g kg^{-1}			Total N g kg^{-1}			Organic N g kg^{-1}		
	Day 0	Day 180	Δ +/-	Day 0	Day 180	Δ +/-	Day 0	Day 180	Δ +/-	Day 0	Day 180	Δ +/-
Raw slurry	4.44 \pm 0.05 d	3.65 \pm 0.27 b	-0.79 a	18.0 \pm 0.54c	14.5 \pm 1.69 d	-3.50 b	2.44 \pm 0.16 a	2.27 \pm 0.09 a	-0.18 b	1.21 \pm 0.17 a	1.05 \pm 0.20 a	-0.16 a
Digestate	6.21 \pm 0.12 e	6.10 \pm 0.08c	-0.11 b	20.3 \pm 0.83 d	20.7 \pm 0.31 e	0.40c	3.28 \pm 0.14c	3.46 \pm 0.04 bc	+0.18 b	1.51 \pm 0.12 a	1.85 \pm 0.11 b	+0.34 a
LF	3.00 \pm 0.03 a	2.84 \pm 0.02 a	-0.16 b	12.2 \pm 0.16 a	12.1 \pm 0.11c	-0.10c	2.94 \pm 0.01 b	2.83 \pm 0.03 b	-0.11 b	1.20 \pm 0.01 a	1.03 \pm 0.21 a	-0.17 a
LFpH-4.27	3.81 \pm 0.11c	3.40 \pm 0.07 b	-0.41 b	11.3 \pm 1.73 a	7.7 \pm 0.60 a	-3.54 b	5.15 \pm 0.21 e	5.33 \pm 0.33 e	+0.18 b	1.19 \pm 0.23 a	1.10 \pm 0.41 a	-0.09 a
LFpH-5.03	3.56 \pm 0.08 b	3.65 \pm 0.05 b	0.09 b	14.6 \pm 0.26 b	7.4 \pm 0.12 a	-7.19 a	4.56 \pm 0.09 de	4.28 \pm 0.34 d	-0.28 b	1.32 \pm 0.10 a	1.72 \pm 0.20 ab	+0.40 a
LFpH-5.42	3.66 \pm 0.02 bc	3.48 \pm 0.05 b	-0.18 b	15.2 \pm 0.88 b	9.7 \pm 0.49 b	-5.50 ab	4.91 \pm 0.04 de	3.86 \pm 0.13 cd	-1.05 a	1.50 \pm 0.05 a	1.48 \pm 0.30a b	-0.03 a
Material	NH_4^+ -N g kg^{-1}			NO_3^- -N g kg^{-1}			NO_2^- -N g kg^{-1}			NH_4^+ + NO_2^- + NO_3^- % of Total N		
	Day 0	Day 180	Δ +/-	Day 0	Day 180	Δ +/-	Day 0	Day 180	Δ +/-	Day 0	Day 180	Δ +/-
Raw slurry	1.23 \pm 0.02 b	1.22 \pm 0.16 ab	-0.01 a	0.01 \pm 0.00 a	0.00 \pm 0.00 a	-0.01 ab	0.00 \pm 0.00 a	0.00 \pm 0.00 a	0.00c	50.6 a	53.8 ab	+3.2 a
Digestate	1.77 \pm 0.02 d	1.60 \pm 0.12 bc	-0.17 a	0.00 \pm 0.00 a	0.00 \pm 0.00 a	0.00 ab	0.00 \pm 0.00 a	0.00 \pm 0.00 a	0.00c	54.0 ab	46.4 a	-7.6 a
LF	1.73 \pm 0.02 d	1.79 \pm 0.18c	+0.06 a	0.01 \pm 0.00 a	0.00 \pm 0.00 a	0.00 ab	0.00 \pm 0.00 a	0.00 \pm 0.00 a	0.00c	59.1 b	59.5 abc	+0.4 a
LFpH-4.27	1.40 \pm 0.01c	1.49 \pm 0.10 bc	+0.08 a	2.37 \pm 0.04 d	2.75 \pm 0.47c	+0.38 b	0.19 \pm 0.01 b	0.02 \pm 0.00 a	-0.17 b	77.0 d	74.9c	-2.1 a
LFpH-5.03	1.11 \pm 0.01 a	0.96 \pm 0.19 a	-0.15 a	1.87 \pm 0.00c	1.47 \pm 0.36 b	-0.40 a	0.26 \pm 0.00 b	0.14 \pm 0.01 b	-0.12 b	71.1 cd	64.0 bc	-7.2 a
LFpH-5.42	1.25 \pm 0.01 b	0.89 \pm 0.15 a	-0.36 a	1.06 \pm 0.10 b	1.10 \pm 0.10 b	+0.04 ab	1.10 \pm 0.09c	0.52 \pm 0.02c	-0.58 a	69.4c	65.7 bc	-3.7 a

The letters indicate significant differences calculated by pairwise comparisons between averages of the treatments (n=3). Means followed by different letters within each column are significantly different ($p < 0.05$).

between days 120 and 150 by 0.32 and 0.33 pH units, respectively (Fig. 1).

After six months of storage, the most significant increase in the plasma-treated materials occurred in LFpH-5.42 by 0.91 pH units > LFpH-5.03 > LFpH-4.27 by 0.60 and 0.22 pH units, respectively. The resulting pH in LFpH-5.42 treatment exceeded pH 6.0 after 120 days, and at the end of the storage experiment, it was 6.33. Plasma treatment to pH = 4.27 resulted in the lowest pH change during the 180 days of storage. The changes in pH in raw slurry and liquid fraction during the storage period were quite similar (Fig. 1, Table S1).

The dry matter content of the organic materials decreased during the 180-day storage period in the range of 1.1–7.9 g kg⁻¹, with a more considerable reduction occurring in the raw slurry. The highest decline in DM content among the plasma-treated samples occurred in LFpH-4.27 by 4.1 g kg⁻¹. Likewise, there was a decline in total carbon content after six months of storage in the range of 0.10–7.19 g kg⁻¹, with the highest reduction occurring in the three plasma-treated digestates (Table 2).

The plasma-treated samples had higher total N content than untreated materials at the end of the storage period, with storage having a variable effect on the total N concentration in the materials. The changes in organic N content during storage were also statistically the same among the treatments, with a tendency to decrease except for the digestate and LFpH-5.03 treatments, whose slight increases could probably be attributed to analytical errors (Table 2).

The NH₄⁺-N concentration remained relatively constant throughout the storage, with most samples exhibiting a decline at the end of day 180 except for LF and LFpH-4.27, which had a slight increase. The highest decrease occurred in LFpH-5.42 and the digestate by 0.36 and 0.17 g kg⁻¹, respectively (Fig. 1a, Table 2). The NO₃-N concentrations remained relatively constant throughout the storage period, with a slight increase (by 0.38 g kg⁻¹) in LFpH-4.27 and a decrease in LFpH-5.03 by -0.38 g kg⁻¹ (Fig. 1b, Table 2). On the

Fig. 2. Evolution of a) NH₄⁺-N, b) NO₃⁻-N and c) NO₂⁻-N in soil amended with a digestate, raw slurry, a liquid fraction (LF) and plasma-treated liquid fractions during incubation at 10 °C for 80 days. Error bars represent standard errors (n = 3).

other hand, the $\text{NO}_2\text{-N}$ concentrations significantly reduced during the 180-day storage period, with the largest decrease occurring in LFpH-5.42 by $0.58 \text{ g NO}_2\text{-N kg}^{-1}$ (Fig. 1b, Table 2).

The changes in nitrogen forms during the storage period had consequential effects on the total inorganic N (% of total N) present in the materials. There was a slight increase in the proportion of inorganic N (% of total N) in raw slurry and LF by 3.2 and 0.4% units, respectively, at the end of 180 days of storage. In contrast, the proportion of inorganic N (% of total N) present in the digestate, LFpH-4.27, LFpH-5.03 and LFpH-5.42 slightly decreased, with the highest reductions occurring in the digestate and LFpH-5.03 (Table 2).

3.3. Effects of plasma treatment on N dynamics and turnover in soil

The soil inorganic nitrogen dynamics and turnover were followed for 80 days after organic material incorporation (Fig. 2, Fig. 3). Application of untreated and plasma-treated digestates to the soil resulted in an immediate significant increase in $\text{NH}_4^+\text{-N}$ content compared to the control (Fig. 2a). Untreated materials (raw slurry, digestate and LF) resulted in the highest $\text{NH}_4^+\text{-N}$ increase of $> 100 \text{ mg NH}_4^+\text{-N kg}^{-1}$, while plasma-treated samples (LFpH-4.27, LFpH-5.03 and LFpH-5.42) had an average increase of $49 \text{ mg NH}_4^+\text{-N kg}^{-1}$ relative to the control. The $\text{NO}_2\text{-N}$ content was negligible in the soil after applying untreated samples, while it was higher in plasma-treated samples. Similarly, incorporating plasma-treated materials into the soil significantly increased the $\text{NO}_3\text{-N}$ content compared to untreated materials (Fig. 2b).

The net inorganic N release (% of applied N) in the soil started to decrease immediately after incorporating the raw slurry and digestate until day 2, where it started to increase again gradually until day 50; after that, it remained relatively constant until the end of incubation. On the contrary, the LF and plasma-treated samples had a different trend, with no reductions observed in the first two days after soil incorporation (Fig. 3).

After the incorporation of raw slurry, digestate and liquid fraction materials, the $\text{NH}_4^+\text{-N}$ concentration decreased steadily until day 28. Concurrently, there was a gradual increase of $\text{NO}_3\text{-N}$ content following the incorporation of the same materials until day 28, where it remained relatively constant until the end of 80 days of incubation (Fig. 2b). In these treatments, the recovered $\text{NH}_4^+\text{-N}$ (% of applied $\text{NH}_4^+\text{-N}$) decreased with time, with the fastest reduction of available soil $\text{NH}_4^+\text{-N}$ occurring in soil applied with raw slurry (Table 3). Conversely, nitrification rates increased with time until the period between days 14 and 28, when they were the highest and, afterwards, started to decline (Table 3).

In the plasma-treated liquid fraction of the digestates (LFpH-4.27, LFpH-5.03 and LFpH-5.42), $\text{NH}_4^+\text{-N}$ and $\text{NO}_3\text{-N}$ concentrations remained constant throughout the incubation period. However, there was an increase in $\text{NO}_3\text{-N}$ concentration in treatment LFpH-5.42 between days 2 and 28, coinciding with a decrease in $\text{NO}_2\text{-N}$ concentrations (Figs. 2b and 2c). The $\text{NH}_4^+\text{-N}$ and $\text{NO}_3\text{-N}$ transformations in the plasma-treated organic materials corresponded well with recoveries of $\text{NH}_4^+\text{-N}$ (% of applied $\text{NH}_4^+\text{-N}$) and nitrification rates throughout the incubation period (Table 3). The $\text{NH}_4^+\text{-N}$ recoveries in relation to applied $\text{NH}_4^+\text{-N}$ were $> 95\%$ throughout the entire incubation period, indicating that no significant $\text{NH}_4^+\text{-N}$ nitrification occurred during the incubation period (Table 3).

On the other hand, the nitrification rates were slightly higher at earlier stages of incubation, during the periods 0–3 days and 3–7 days; this could be linked to the nitrification of $\text{NO}_2\text{-N}$ present in the plasma treated digestates. A higher nitrification rate of $2.55 \pm 0.30 \text{ mg (NO}_3\text{-N} + \text{NO}_2\text{-N) kg}^{-1} \text{ day}^{-1}$ was recorded in the period between days 7 and 14 for treatment LFpH-5.42 relative to low nitrification rates for LFpH-4.27 and LFpH-5.03 during the same period (Table 3). The high rate coincides with a decline in $\text{NO}_2\text{-N}$ concentrations measured in soil up to day 28 following the incorporation of LFpH-5.42. Significant differences were observed in nitrification rates between plasma-treated digestates and untreated materials for the entire 80 days of incubation (Table 3). Notably, nitrite was only detected and measured in soil samples incorporated with plasma-treated materials, and it decreased to zero after 7–28 days (Fig. 2c).

Fig. 3. Net inorganic N release (% of N input) in soil amended with raw slurry, a digestate, a liquid fraction (LF) and plasma-treated liquid fractions at different pH during incubation at 10°C for 80 days. Error bars represent standard deviation ($n = 3$). The letters indicate significant differences calculated by pairwise comparisons between averages of the treatments ($n=3$).

Table 3

Recovery of NH_4^+ -N (% of applied NH_4^+ -N) in soil (a) and nitrification rates (b), $\text{mg} (\text{NO}_3\text{-N} + \text{NO}_2\text{-N}) \text{kg}^{-1} \text{day}^{-1}$ of organic manures during the 80 days of incubation at 10 °C. Values correspond to means \pm standard deviation (n=3).

a) Recovered NH_4^+ -N (% of applied NH_4^+)						
Days	Raw slurry	Digestate	LF	LFpH-4.27	LFpH-5.03	LFpH-5.42
0	100.1 \pm 1.6 a	102.1 \pm 9.2 a	95.7 \pm 3.7 a	96.2 \pm 3.7 a	94.2 \pm 0.1 a	93.1 \pm 4.1 a
3	75.9 \pm 1.6 a	93.6 \pm 4.4 b	94.9 \pm 1.0 b	96.3 \pm 1.3 b	96.0 \pm 0.8 b	92.8 \pm 0.7 b
7	75.5 \pm 2.1 a	88.8 \pm 2.7 b	91.0 \pm 0.6 b	97.4 \pm 0.7c	99.6 \pm 2.3c	97.2 \pm 0.8c
14	49.3 \pm 0.6 a	63.1 \pm 3.6 b	62.1 \pm 3.1 b	96.8 \pm 0.9c	98.9 \pm 0.9c	99.4 \pm 0.8c
28	0.4 \pm 0.1 a	0.7 \pm 0.1 b	1.1 \pm 0.0 b	97.4 \pm 1.7c	98.5 \pm 2.0c	101.3 \pm 1.9c
50	0.1 \pm 0.0 a	0.2 \pm 0.1 a	0.2 \pm 0.1 a	99.7 \pm 1.7 b	101.1 \pm 0.3 b	98.1 \pm 4.3 b
80	0.1 \pm 0.1 a	0.1 \pm 0.0 a	0.2 \pm 0.0 a	103.8 \pm 3.4 b	101.5 \pm 2.2 b	101.4 \pm 1.3 b
b) Nitrification rates ($\text{mg N kg}^{-1} \text{day}^{-1}$)						
Days	Raw slurry	Digestate	LF	LFpH-4.27	LFpH-5.03	LFpH-5.42
0–3	0.77 \pm 0.11 a	1.18 \pm 0.05 ab	0.85 \pm 0.19 a	1.66 \pm 0.57 b	1.41 \pm 0.38 ab	4.77 \pm 0.47c
3–7	2.11 \pm 0.19 b	1.94 \pm 0.17 b	2.23 \pm 0.33 b	0.37 \pm 0.72 a	1.72 \pm 0.36 b	2.71 \pm 0.21 b
7–14	4.65 \pm 0.20c	4.93 \pm 0.39c	5.47 \pm 0.18c	0.13 \pm 0.41 a	-0.36 \pm 0.41 a	2.55 \pm 0.30 b
14–28	4.08 \pm 0.11c	4.67 \pm 0.34c	5.34 \pm 0.14c	0.08 \pm 0.09 a	0.24 \pm 0.12 ab	0.33 \pm 0.13 b
28–50	0.40 \pm 0.05 ab	0.31 \pm 0.20 ab	0.49 \pm 0.01 b	0.12 \pm 0.11 a	0.13 \pm 0.09 a	0.25 \pm 0.16 ab
50–80	0.08 \pm 0.05 a	0.10 \pm 0.10 a	0.11 \pm 0.07 a	0.16 \pm 0.01 a	0.12 \pm 0.01 a	0.10 \pm 0.07 a
0–80	1.40 \pm 0.03c	1.52 \pm 0.03c	1.73 \pm 0.03c	0.18 \pm 0.02 a	0.25 \pm 0.07 a	0.71 \pm 0.02 b

Means followed by different letters within each row are significantly different ($p < 0.05$).

Following a 80-day incubation period, the net inorganic N release in soil (% of N input) from the organic materials was significantly different (Fig. 3, Table S1). The raw slurry had the lowest net inorganic N release at 50 % (of total N input), whereas LFpH-4.27 had the highest at 78% (of N input). Anaerobic co-digestion of raw slurry with solid biomasses increased the net inorganic N release by 5 % relative to the raw cattle slurry, whereas digestate separation increased the inorganic N release in the liquid fraction by 9%. The plasma treatment increased the net inorganic N release by 5–14 % units relative to LF, with the highest increase occurring in LFpH-4.27. Plasma treatment to attain pH 5.03 or 5.42 did not significantly vary the inorganic N released into the soil (Fig. 3, Table S1). The largest N mineralisation (% of applied organic N) was observed in the LF, where net inorganic N release (% of applied organic N) increased by 1.2%.

Adding untreated organic materials (raw slurry, digestate and LF) to the soil increased the soil pH by 0.73 pH units on average relative to the control at day 0 (Table 4). After that, it decreased until day 28, where it remained constant until day 80. For acidified materials, the soil pH decreased by 0.28 pH units immediately after incorporating the materials, followed by a short-lived increase until day 14 (Table 4, Figure S1). Afterwards, the pH decreased until day 28 and remained pretty constant until the last day of the incubation. The soil pH applied with non-acidified LF decreased by 1.61 units after 80 days of incorporation, whereas that of acidified LF decreased by only 0.14–0.23 units (Table 4).

4. Discussion

4.1. Changes in organic materials' characteristics after plasma treatment and during storage period

The amount of acid or additive required to decrease the pH of the slurry to a specific target pH is variable. It depends on the acid/additive characteristics and the buffering capacity of the slurry, which is also dependent on the contents of ammoniacal nitrogen, carbonates, phosphates and volatile fatty acids present (Sommer & Husted, 2009). The buffering capacity is highest in digestates from biogas production due to a high content of carbonates (Sommer & Husted, 1995). In this study, three different pH levels were obtained

Table 4

Soil pH (measured in 1 M KCl) during 80 days of incubation following soil amendment with raw slurry, digestate, the liquid fraction of separated digestate (LF) and plasma-treated liquid fractions at different initial target pH. The control represents unamended soil.

Material	Days of incubation						
	0	3	7	14	28	50	80
Control soil	5.80 \pm 0.10 b	5.93 \pm 0.02c	5.69 \pm 0.15 a	5.79 \pm 0.04 a	5.22 \pm 0.01 d	5.17 \pm 0.03c	5.17 \pm 0.01 cd
Raw slurry	6.43 \pm 0.05c	6.42 \pm 0.01 d	6.28 \pm 0.10 bc	6.16 \pm 0.06c	5.09 \pm 0.04c	5.09 \pm 0.02 b	5.13 \pm 0.02 bc
Digestate	6.61 \pm 0.18c	6.50 \pm 0.06 d	6.43 \pm 0.06c	6.28 \pm 0.06 d	5.00 \pm 0.05 b	5.04 \pm 0.02 b	5.10 \pm 0.05 b
LF	6.55 \pm 0.02 c	6.46 \pm 0.06 d	6.43 \pm 0.02 c	6.31 \pm 0.01 d	4.87 \pm 0.01 a	4.92 \pm 0.02 a	4.94 \pm 0.01 a
LFpH-4.27	5.37 \pm 0.02 a	5.40 \pm 0.02 a	5.76 \pm 0.07 a	6.04 \pm 0.06 b	5.23 \pm 0.01 d	5.21 \pm 0.01 cd	5.23 \pm 0.02 de
LFpH-5.03	5.60 \pm 0.02 b	5.67 \pm 0.06 b	5.97 \pm 0.21 ab	6.05 \pm 0.01 bc	5.30 \pm 0.04 d	5.26 \pm 0.01 d	5.24 \pm 0.00 e
LFpH-5.42	5.60 \pm 0.03 b	5.68 \pm 0.05 b	5.86 \pm 0.21 a	5.99 \pm 0.03 b	5.43 \pm 0.04 e	5.40 \pm 0.04 e	5.37 \pm 0.02 f

The letters indicate significant differences calculated by pairwise comparisons between averages of the treatments on each day (n=3). Means followed by different letters within each column are significantly different ($p < 0.05$).

by varying the treatment intensity of the slurry in the plasma. The liquid fraction (LF) was acidified to pH \approx 5.5 based on common practice by slurry acidification in barns in Denmark, and two lower pH levels, pH 5.03 and pH 4.27, to compare the effects of plasma-assisted acidification on pH stability during six-month storage. Unlike acidification with a strong acid like H₂SO₄, where substantial amounts of foam are produced during acidification due to the formation of CO₂, no foam is formed during plasma treatment. This could, therefore, reduce the need for 0.5–1 m extra space in the storage tanks above the slurry usually needed for acid-based acidification to avoid foam overflow (Lemes et al., 2022).

The decrease in pH was positively correlated with the amount of NO₃ fixed in the slurry and inversely related to the NO₂ content (Fig. 2, Table 2). Therefore, the lower the pH of plasma-treated digestate, the more NO₃ is fixed and the less NO₂. The decreasing NO₂-N levels with a decrease in pH could be explained by peroxyxynitrite reactions, where acidity plays a key role in the stability of NO₃, NO₂ and H₂O₂ (Graves et al., 2018; Ranieri et al., 2021). In this case, the reactivity of the NO₂ increases with a decrease in pH to form the more stable NO₃-N in the slurry ($3\text{NO}_2 + 3\text{H}^+ \rightarrow 2\text{NO} + \text{NO}_3 + \text{H}_3\text{O}^+$). The NO formed reacts with NO₂ in the slurry to form additional NO₂ (Graves et al., 2018). Contrary to sulphuric acid-based acidification, where total N concentration in the acidified materials does not change, plasma treatment adds inorganic N (NO₃-N + NO₂-N) to the slurry, which is readily available for crop uptake, potentially replacing more synthetic N fertilisers if appropriately used.

Alongside acidification reducing NH₃ emissions, it changes the physical properties of the slurry (Hjorth et al., 2015), and it can reduce CH₄ emissions from slurry during storage, as it inhibits methane-forming microorganisms (Fangueiro et al., 2015b; Petersen et al., 2012). Regueiro et al. (2016) found higher NH₄⁺-N in the acidified slurries by adding different additives compared to a non-acidified raw slurry, with slurry acidified to pH 3.5 having higher NH₄⁺-N throughout the storage period for 60 days. However, in our study, we found contrasting results, whereby the NH₄⁺-N content in the plasma-treated digestates was lower compared to untreated liquid fraction (LF) by a third. The lower NH₄⁺-N in plasma-treated samples could possibly be explained by the oxidation of part of NH₄⁺-N present in the liquid fraction to NO₃-N and NO₂-N, favoured by the presence of oxygen ($\text{NH}_4^+ + 2\text{O}_2 \rightarrow \text{NO}_2 + 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$; $2\text{NO}_2 + \text{O}_2 \rightarrow 2\text{NO}_3$). A similar trend was observed by Björs (2023) in plasma-treated manure samples.

The evolution of slurry pH during storage is highly variable and is dependent on numerous variables, i.e. initial pH, storage period, slurry type, storage temperatures, type of acid/ additive, covered or uncovered storage facilities, slurry aeration, among others (Adamsen et al., 2021; Fangueiro et al., 2015a; Sørensen & Eriksen, 2009). Our findings revealed that long-term pH stability and a one-time extended acidification effect by plasma treatment could be attained by acidifying the slurry to pH \approx 5.0 or lower. However, a more constant pH was achieved when the slurry was acidified to pH 4.27, which could be attributed to the inhibition of microbial activities at lower pH levels. Our results align with those of Regueiro et al. (2016), who found a constant pH when they acidified slurry to a lower pH of 3.5 compared to pH 5.5. The highest increase in pH occurred in LFpH-5.42 from pH 5.42–6.33, possibly requiring a re-acidification before field application (Pedersen et al., 2022). Sørensen and Eriksen (2009) observed a similar trend with sulphuric acid-based acidification, where pH increased from 5.5 to about 6.0–6.2 within weeks, whereas Petersen et al. (2012) observed a pH increase from pH around 4.5 to pH 6.0 after 90 days of slurry storage.

The increase in pH in slurries during storage could be linked to either degradation of dissociated organic acids resulting in an evolution of CO₂, mineralisation of organic N or dissolution of the carbonates (Petersen et al., 2012; Regueiro et al., 2022), associated with microbial activities. The unexpected reduction in pH in the digestate after 30 days of storage, which remained relatively constant after day 90, could be explained by a trade-off between the production and oxidation of volatile fatty acids (Perazzolo et al., 2017). The digestate was sourced from a thermophilic digester, and the drastic changes from thermophilic to psychrophilic storage temperatures could have probably inhibited the activity of the temperature-sensitive methanogenic consortia, limiting further degradation of accumulated volatile fatty acids, resulting in a slight pH drop.

The observed increase in the dry matter content immediately after plasma treatment could be explained by the extra NO₃-N and NO₂-N fixed. A similar trend was reported by Sørensen and Eriksen (2009), Kai et al. (2008) and Regueiro et al. (2016) in sulphuric acid-based and bio-acidification of slurries after the addition of acids and additives. Losses, i.e. of nitrogen in different forms and CO₂ evolution associated with the degradation of organic matter, could probably explain the reduction in dry matter after six months of storage. Moreover, acidification could induce hydrolysis of the organic matter in the slurries, resulting in the degradation of the cellulose and hemicellulose into soluble sugars (Hjorth et al., 2015). The sugars could be converted and evolved as CO₂ from the storage tanks, reducing the carbon and dry matter contents. A decline in organic nitrogen could also be linked to degradation of organic N during the storage period.

Acidification generally maintains equilibrium in favour of non-volatile NH₄⁺ throughout the storage period, hindering NH₃ losses via volatilisation. The slight changes observed in NH₄⁺-N, particularly for the raw slurry and the digestate, could be linked to NH₃ losses during the storage. Results also revealed a reduction in NO₂-N in the plasma-treated samples at the end of the storage period, with the highest reduction occurring in LFpH-5.42. The decline could probably be explained by either partial oxidation of NO₂-N to NO₃-N, which seems to correlate with an increase in NO₃-N content, especially for LFpH-4.27 or losses via NO/N₂O emissions. The NO₂ is an unstable anion that could easily be oxidised to NO₃ under acidic conditions or reduced to N₂O in the denitrification pathway if anaerobic conditions exist in the storage containers. However, we could not directly link the reduction in NO₂-N to N₂O emissions as it was not measured in this experiment. The possible N losses during storage, as depicted by the reductions in total N concentrations (Table 2), ultimately resulted in a decline in the proportion of inorganic N present in the plasma-treated samples.

4.2. Effects of plasma treatment on N dynamics and turnover in soil

Generally, the plasma treatment of slurries resulted in the highest net inorganic N release (% of N applied) in the soil after 80 days of incubation. The higher net inorganic N release than untreated slurries could be explained by the extra readily available inorganic N

(NO₂-N to NO₃-N) fixed by the plasma. The observed short-term decrease in inorganic N release to the soil after two days of incorporation of raw slurry and a digestate could be attributed to the microbial assimilation of inorganic N associated with the decomposition of decomposable organic matter present in the two materials (Kirchmann & Lundvall, 1993). Comparatively, the plasma-treated materials and liquid fraction (LF) did not show any decline in the inorganic N release at the same period, which could be explained by the low quantities of decomposable organic matter present.

The study reveals that plasma treatment of digestates significantly influences the nitrification process following incorporation. The high recovery of NH₄⁺-N throughout the 80 days of incubation demonstrates that the plasma treatment stopped NH₄⁺-N nitrification in the soil. The delay in nitrification may be attributed to the toxic compounds, such as hydrogen peroxide and peroxy nitrite, that were added to the slurry during plasma treatment (Graves et al., 2018). High concentrations of hydrogen peroxide can be toxic to nitrifying bacteria, such as Nitrosomonas and Nitrobacter, which play critical roles in the nitrification process. The oxidative stress caused by hydrogen peroxide can inhibit the activity of these bacteria, potentially slowing down or disrupting the nitrification process. However, the actual effects of components of plasma-treated slurry on nitrifying bacteria need further investigation.

The higher transient nitrification rates observed in the first few days could be linked to the oxidation of unstable NO₂ fixed by the plasma during treatment. The prolonged inhibition of nitrification could have further triggered shifts in microbial communities in soil, i.e. nitrifying bacteria declining and other bacteria becoming dominant, further delaying recovery of the nitrification process. A delay in NH₄⁺-N nitrification could potentially reduce nitrogen losses via leaching and reduce N₂O emissions linked to nitrification-denitrification processes (Qiao et al., 2015). Similar inhibition of NH₄⁺-N nitrification in soil by plasma treatment of slurry to pH 4.4 has been reported by Björs (2023) over six weeks, a shorter period than in this study. Fangueiro et al. (2016) similarly reported a short-lived delay of NH₄⁺-N nitrification for 8–15 days, albeit with sulphuric acid-based acidification.

This study demonstrates that alongside the plasma treatment technique reducing slurry pH, it concurrently adds variable NO₂-N and NO₃-N contents to the soil depending on the treatment time and intensity, positively increasing the nitrogen fertiliser value of the slurry. Nonetheless, this technique creates a risk for potential pollution swapping. For instance, it increases the risk of the added N to be lost via NO/N₂O emissions in the denitrification process or through NO₃ leaching. A study by Cottis et al. (2023) revealed that plasma-treated slurries resulted in a 20–30% higher yield than untreated cattle slurry when both applied at the same total N rates. However, they could not account for 17% of N in the plasma-treated slurry.

Nitrite in the soil is regarded as toxic to plant growth and metabolism, and its toxicity effect is more pronounced when it exists in equilibrium with free nitrous acid (Lee, 1979). In this study, nitrite was detected in soil between days 7 and 28 after amendment, with the most prolonged presence occurring in the LFPH-5.42. The high NO₂ levels, coupled with high NH₄⁺ content in the plasma-treated digestates, may cause adverse effects on root development, especially at earlier stages of plant growth (Van Cleemput & Samater, 1995). Pedersen et al. (2020) observed damages to the primary roots of young maize plants 21 and 35 days after cattle slurry application, and they attributed the root damage to a possible toxic effect of nitrite, formed as an intermediary in the denitrification process. However, the study could not delink the damage from NH₄⁺-N toxicity, which was equally present at high concentrations.

In the untreated samples (raw slurry, digestate and LF), a gradual decline in the NH₄⁺-N content observed in the first 28 days could be attributed to nitrification (Sørensen, 1998). Concurrently, NO₃-N increased from day 0–28, where it remained constant until the end of the incubation period. The changes in N forms due to nitrification simultaneously resulted in a decreasing trend of soil pH until day 28, when it remained steady (Table 4). After day 50, soil pH was nearly the same in all treatments, with the plasma-treated digestates significantly having higher pH. The presence of decomposable organic matter in the digestate, probably due to incomplete breakdown during the AD process, may induce long-term N immobilisation by soil microbial biomass, as seen in the digestate treatment (Table S2). These findings corroborate those of Nyang'au et al. (2023), who observed a similar trend when they incorporated a digestate from a co-digestion of cattle manure and non-ensiled straw. The increasing shift towards using recalcitrant solid biomass such as straw and deep litter in biogas plants, notwithstanding having positive benefits in increasing renewable biogas energy, negatively affects the fertiliser value of the digestates.

4.3. Practical perspectives

The fixation of nitrate and nitrite during plasma treatment, alongside decreasing ammonia volatilisation, improves the nitrogen fertiliser value of the slurries. Consequently, plasma-treated slurry can potentially replace more mineral N fertilisers and minimize environmental problems associated with ammonia volatilization. An extended inhibition of nitrification in soil was found after applying plasma-treated digestates, which could potentially reduce nitrate leaching. Moreover, the technique offers an additional opportunity to reduce odour, sterilize slurry and reduce methane emissions during slurry storage (Graves et al., 2018). Therefore, coupling plasma-assisted acidification to biogas plants could significantly increase environmental benefits by increasing the fertiliser value of the digestates and reduce residual CH₄ and NH₃ emissions following digestate storage and field application.

However, plasma treatment technology relies on an intense electricity-driven plasma that may be higher than the energy consumption required to produce similar amounts of nitrogen in commercial fertilisers. The energy should be considered when evaluating its potential use, and it may vary depending on the utilisation of surplus electricity at a relatively low price. For instance, it could be used in periods with high electricity supply from wind and solar, thereby low electricity prices.

5. Conclusions

This study highlights the potential of plasma treatment as a one-time acidification strategy for slurry to reduce ammonia emissions during storage and after application. Notably, achieving pH levels of 4.27 and 5.03 during treatment resulted in a more stable pH

during the storage. The plasma-treated liquid fraction exhibited a significant increase in fixed nitrogen content, enhancing inorganic N availability upon soil application by 5–14% compared to untreated liquid fraction. The observed inhibition of NH_4^+ -N nitrification was unexpected, and further studies are needed to understand the underlying mechanisms.

It is crucial to address potential risks, particularly the elevated nitrite concentrations, which may threaten early-stage plant development, especially to roots. Further investigations should also be directed towards understanding the effects of mixing plasma-treated slurry with untreated slurry prior to field application and the potential effects of mixing on N_2O emissions, NH_3 losses and ultimate inorganic N availability.

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CRedit authorship contribution statement

Jared Onyango Nyang'au: Writing – original draft, Visualization, Software, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Peter Sørensen:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Supervision, Resources, Project administration, Methodology, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization. **Henrik Bjarne Møller:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Resources, Project administration, Methodology, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data Availability

Data will be made available on request.

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Appendix A. Supporting information

Supplementary data associated with this article can be found in the online version at [doi:10.1016/j.eti.2024.103578](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eti.2024.103578).

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